

SCIENTIFIC-HISTORICAL FOUNDATIONS OF ART HISTORY

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Abstract

Art studies as a separate discipline was formed during the 16th-19th centuries. It is known that information about art was first studied in Greece since ancient times. There is information that great philosophers of that time, such as Aristotle and Plato, were also involved in the history of art in Greece. It means that ancient Rome paid great attention to Greek art.

Key words: art history, nature, architect, coherence, aesthetics, consciousness.

Art studies is a set of social sciences dealing with the study and research of the artistic culture of society, art in general. The science of aesthetics shows that beauty is a necessary condition of art, and that art cannot exist without beauty. Content and form cannot be separated in art. The unique feature of art is its reflection of reality in artistic images from an advanced ideological point of view. The artistic form of art is language, style, and image, which serve to express content. The artistic and creative activity of a person is diverse and it is manifested in art types or genres. They, in turn, can have a number of appearances. In general, art is a historical system consisting of a set of methods of artistic-image understanding of the world, which have different general and specific features. Art is one of the forms of social consciousness, a component of human spiritual culture, a special type of spiritual understanding of the world. Different forms of art reflect reality, events, things and situations in it using their own methods (for example, in music - through sounds, their interconnection, harmony, in fiction - words, through images). But at the same time, there is a certain commonality between them. This commonality consists in the fact that in all of them reality is reflected in an artistic - figurative way. The issue of understanding art and determining its role in people's lives has been the cause of sharp debates and disputes throughout the history of culture. For example, some artists and art critics consider it an "imitation of nature" or "a reflection of reality", while others consider art to be "a purely personal creative product of the artist", "self-expression"., who knew that. This is explained by the complexity of the subject of art, its characteristics and forms, the variety of methods of embodiment, and the differences between the class and ideological opinions of art theorists in different periods. The category of beauty is important in art. Art has a very ancient history. It began to appear in the first stages of the development of the society in connection with the process of cocktailing and the development of people's social activities. This complex includes literary studies (including philological sciences), musicology, theater studies, film studies and art studies in a narrow sense. Art history in the narrow sense is a social science that deals with the study of visual arts, applied and decorative arts and architecture, and when we say art history, it is often

understood in this sense. is held and widely used. Art in this sense has three interrelated branches:

It consists of art theory, art history, art criticism. Art studies, in general, within these branches, the relationship of art to existence, its historical development, social role, its connection with the objective laws of the historical development of society, the influence of the social system and the level of production forces on art and architecture, studies issues related to the nature and forms of art. It describes the creative ways of artists, analyzes, popularizes and promotes works of art.

Art studies as a separate discipline was formed during the 16th-19th centuries. It is known that information about art was first studied in Greece since ancient times. There is information that great philosophers of that time, such as Aristotle and Plato, were also involved in the history of art in Greece. Ancient Rome paid great attention to Greek art. In the early centuries AD, treatises on architecture and art were created in the countries of Central Asia. They were universal in terms of content, they served as both methodological manuals and textbooks, history, stories, advice and observations were brought to the reader's attention. In Europe in the Middle Ages, art became a part of theology. Art historians of the Middle Ages assessed art as a material representation of the other world in this world. The Renaissance period entered history as an important period in the development of art. In the 14th-16th centuries, along with the ideas of humanism and realism, the desire to separate art under the influence of the church increased and an important step was taken towards its scientific description. Many pamphlets created during this period provided basic guidance to artists and sculptors, valuable works on art, its theory and history were created. Artists and architects such as Leonardo da Vinci express such important ideas as painting, its scientific foundations and possibilities, and the reflection of human spiritual life in fine art. In the 16th century, A. Dürer's scientific ideas about proportions in Germany, and P. Aretino's requirements for artists in Venice to accurately reflect existence, made an important contribution to art. In the 17th century, pamphlets, manuals, reviews on European art, guides to Italy, life and creative work of artists, and literature on artistic lifestyle were created. The formation of art as an independent science since the 18th century was connected with the struggle of ideas against the old order and feudalism during the preparation and implementation of the French bourgeois revolution at the end of this century. As a result of the development of socio-critical thinking, the critical etude genre was formed, and the struggle for idealism and realism in art intensified. In Germany, G.E. Lessing introduced the term "fine art" to science as a theoretician of realism. In the 19th century, the scientific-historical foundations of art were strengthened, art was formed as a science and perfected, and acquired its own methodology. In France, the works of Stendhal, G. Courbet, and in Germany I. Goethe and H. Heyne play a major role in art history, the scope of archaeological research has expanded, and art museums have been opened. In this period, especially the ideas of the great French revolution, I. Kant, A. Schopenhauer, G. F. Hegel's aesthetic views, and in Russia V. V. Stasov, I. N. Kramskoi, I. E. Repin and others' valuable ideas about the vitality of art and creative freedom, The ideas of V. G. Belinsky, A. I. Gersen became important in the development of the realistic direction of art. Also, during this period, art developed in a strong relationship with religion. Masterpieces of world art - great architectural structures, images of Virgil, Dante, Milton, Leonardo da Vinci, Raphael, Michelangelo, music of I.S. Bach, I. Haydn, V. A. Mozart, and in the East F. Attor, J. Rumi, A. Jami, A. Navoi's works were inspired

by religious sources. Art plays a special role in the process of instilling the ideology of national independence into the minds of young people. Also, art is one of the tools that expands a person's spiritual outlook and educates him as a person. Art is a means of communication necessary for the movement of humanity towards goodness, and connects different continents and countries. Art does not reflect people's feelings and thoughts in an abstract way, but in live artistic images, it is a treasure of unique emotions. Art is fully manifested in the medium of artistic images. The artistic image is seen in the unity of the outer world mastered by the artist and his inner world. Talented actors can create a scene of true life, entertain with their feelings and experiences, and fully express themselves. Nothing compares to an artistic image that is filled with the inner experiences of the artist. The internal and external aspects of the artistic image apply in different ways in the types of art. In the types of interpretative arts such as theater, music, cinema, "mirror world", the artistic image depends on the process of interpreting the image of that image. Here, the product of the writer's or composer's work, the interpretation of the artistic images created by them, emerges due to the skill of the artist. For example: Abror Hidoyatov, Sora Eshontorayeva, Hamza Umarov, Razzaq Hamroyev, Olim Khojayev, Zaynab Sadriyeva, Nabi Rahimov performed "Navoiy", "Jalaluddin Manguberdi", "Othello", "Hamlet", "King Lear", "Nurkhan", "Mother-in-law", "Father" are an example of this. The broader the artist's worldview and the richer his mental experience, the more effective and meaningful his work will be. Perception of art always gives a person the opportunity to better understand himself, a work of art is a product of individual creativity.

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